

Brain region	LTI quails		STI quails		Statistical values		
	Left-H	Right-H	Left-H	Right-H	Line	Hemisphere	Interaction
Midbrain	1.059 ± 0.06	1.051 ± 0.071	<u>1.15 ± 0.051</u>	<u>1.138 ± 0.035</u>	F=14.735 p=0.001	F=1.057 p=0.318	F=0.036, p=0.851
Preoptic area	0.187 ± 0.013	0.191 ± 0.017	<u>0.203 ± 0.016</u>	<u>0.203 ± 0.018</u>	F=4.448 p=0.049	F=0.548 p=0.469	F=0.845 p=0.37
Preisthmus region of the midbrain	0.151 ± 0.01	0.118 ± 0.012	<u>0.183 ± 0.009</u>	<u>0.148 ± 0.015</u>	F=39.647 p<0.0001	F=330.034 p<0.0001	F=0.456 p=0.508
Apical hyperpallium	1.99 ± 0.113	2.029 ± 0.121	2.074 ± 0.093	2.138 ± 0.125	F=4.091, p=0.058	F=9.569 p=0.006	F=0.522 p=0.479
Nidopallium	8.34 ± 0.372	8.536 ± 0.364	8.066 ± 0.311	8.325 ± 0.291	F=2.957 p=0.103	F=18.204 p=0.0005	F=0.348 p=0.562
Ambiguous nucleus	0.012 ± 0.002	0.014 ± 0.002	0.011 ± 0.002	0.014 ± 0.002	F=0.662, p=0.426	F=29.588 p<0.0001	F=0.657 p=0.428
Anterior pretectal and subpretectal nuclei	0.174 ± 0.017	0.162 ± 0.014	0.176 ± 0.015	0.16 ± 0.015	F=0 p=0.999	F=42.136 p<0.0001	F=0.646 p=0.432
Striatopallidal area	0.074 ± 0.005	0.067 ± 0.005	0.08 ± 0.008	0.07 ± 0.006	F=3.824 p=0.066	F=49.132 p<0.0001	F=0.811 p=0.38
Semilunar nucleus	0.052 ± 0.007	0.039 ± 0.004	0.055 ± 0.005	0.041 ± 0.004	F=1.486 p=0.239	F=145.881 p<0.0001	F=0.277 p=0.605
Ventral tegmental area	0.066 ± 0.006	0.059 ± 0.004	0.067 ± 0.007	0.059 ± 0.005	F=0.281 p=0.603	F=20.262 p=0.0003	F=0.012 p=0.913
Caudal hindbrain	2.942 ± 0.196	2.721 ± 0.208	2.964 ± 0.176	2.737 ± 0.181	F=0.052 p=0.823	F=164.425 p<0.0001	F=0.025 p=0.877
Lateral preoptic area	0.141 ± 0.011	0.141 ± 0.007	0.155 ± 0.011	0.142 ± 0.014	F=3.599 p=0.074	F=3.581 p=0.075	F=4.354 p=0.051
Rostral hindbrain #	0.814 ± 0.044	0.777 ± 0.043	0.838 ± 0.043	0.808 ± 0.033			
Lateral pontine nucleus #	0.08 ± 0.01	0.066 ± 0.005	0.075 ± 0.007	0.07 ± 0.011			
Unknown rostralateral band #	0.042 ± 0.003	0.043 ± 0.002	0.043 ± 0.004	0.042 ± 0.004			
Lateral forebrain bundle	0.073 ± 0.004	0.088 ± 0.005	0.077 ± 0.005	0.09 ± 0.006	F=2.997 p=0.101	F=230.682 p<0.0001	F=0.807 p=0.381
Medial forebrain bundle	0.046 ± 0.003	0.055 ± 0.003	<u>0.051 ± 0.004</u>	0.06 ± 0.005	F=9.429 p=0.007	F=114.559 p<0.0001	F=0.003 p=0.956
Nigrostriatal tract	0.051 ± 0.003	0.06 ± 0.005	0.051 ± 0.003	0.059 ± 0.004	F=0.247 p=0.625	F=70.433 p<0.0001	F=0.426 p=0.522
Tectothalamic tract	0.191 ± 0.019	0.211 ± 0.019	<u>0.207 ± 0.013</u>	0.234 ± 0.018	F=6.976 p=0.017	F=89.953 p<0.0001	F=2.042 p=0.17
Corticomesencephalic tract	0.239 ± 0.014	0.237 ± 0.02	0.23 ± 0.014	0.227 ± 0.012	F=2.241 p=0.152	F=0.559 p=0.464	F=0.015 p=0.904
Amygdalofugal tract	0.101 ± 0.009	0.105 ± 0.01	0.108 ± 0.008	0.111 ± 0.009	F=3.351 p=0.084	F=3.345 p=0.084	F=0.044 p=0.836
Quintofrontal tract	0.015 ± 0.002	0.015 ± 0.002	0.016 ± 0.001	0.016 ± 0.002	F=2.369 p=0.141	F=2.046 p=0.17	F=0.128 p=0.725
Medial longitudinal fasciculus	0.167 ± 0.015	0.172 ± 0.015	0.167 ± 0.016	0.167 ± 0.014	F=0.206 p=0.656	F=0.675 p=0.422	F=0.946 p=0.344
Subgeniculate nuclei #	0.171 ± 0.019	0.155 ± 0.016	0.161 ± 0.016	0.146 ± 0.016			
Pallium ##	1.823 ± 0.135	1.735 ± 0.157	1.745 ± 0.058	1.691 ± 0.114			
Interhemispheric region							
Region	LTI quail	STI quail	Statistical values (Line Effect)				
Mammillary bodies ##	0.069 ± 0.008	0.07 ± 0.005					
Anterior commissure	0.077 ± 0.008	0.075 ± 0.006	t=0.6799, p=0.505				

Posterior commissure #	0.054 ± 0.005	0.064 ± 0.02	
Vestibular commissure	0.1 ± 0.008	0.097 ± 0.008	t=0.8353, p=0.414
Decussation of the solitary tract	0.023 ± 0.003	0.023 ± 0.002	t=-0.0097, p=0.992
Ventricle #	6.359 ± 0.283	6.445 ± 0.307	